

Design and Development of Multi-Purpose Crop Cutting Machine

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ABSTRACT

The small-scale farmers who have land area of less than 2 acres this machine will be beneficial for them. This machine is compact and can be very useful to cut finger millet and horse gram crops. It has cutting blades which cut the crop in a scissoring type of motion. It runs on electric motor of 250W, this power from Battery. A collecting mechanism is provided for the collection of crops to one side of it after cutting. The pulley arrangement is to provide power to this mechanism. It is easily maintainable as this compact harvester is manufactured using locally available spare parts.

This harvester might be the solution to the problems faced by a small-scale farmer regarding labour implementation and cost. After testing this machine in farm, it is found that the cost of harvesting using this harvester is considerably much less as compare to manual harvesting.

Keywords: Crop Cutting, Harvester, Finger millet, Horse gram, Scissoring

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently rural has seen a shortage of skilled labour available for agriculture. Because of this shortage the farmers have transitioned to using harvesters. These harvesters are available for purchase but they are not affordable because of their high costs, however, agriculture groups make these available for rent on an hourly basis. But the small holding farm owners i.e. generally having land less than 2 Acres generally do not require the full-featured combine harvesters. Due to financial or transportation reasons these combine harvesters are not available in all parts of rural area. Thus, there is a need for a smaller and efficient combine harvester which would be considerably cheaper and also more accessible. The mission is to create a portable, low-cost mini harvester and user-friendly. These problems gave us the basic idea about what was required in the current situation. The idea was to create a machine which will reduce the labour required to harvest crops and which is cheap. This machine has the capability and the economic value for fulfilling the needs of farmers having small land holdings which is less than 2 acres. This machine is cost effective and also easy to maintain and repair for farmers.

Fig. 1: Manual Crop cutting

2. Objective of the Project

- To design and develop a crop cutter operated on automatic power for the ease of crop cutting at higher rate.
- Designing with load calculation a robust and versatile machine that can be adopted for cutting finger millet and horse gram crops.
- Testing the model under real-world conditions to ensure its reliability, efficiency and safety.

3. Methodology

Fig.2: Methodology

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This crop cutting machine required less human effort and it very reasonable for middle class farmer it is not complicated structure and it easily operated by unskilled person. It can reduce labour cost due to the only one person can handle the machine. Crop cutter machine does not require high life support.

This machine targets the small-scale farmers who have land area of smaller than 2 or 3 acres. This

mechanism is compact and can cut up to two rows of Finger Millet and Horse Gram crops with 360-degree camera. It has cutting blades which cut the crop in a scissoring type of movement. It runs on battery, this power from Motor is provided through shaft and chain drive system to the cutting blades. This compact crop cutter is manufactured using locally available spare parts and thus, it is easily maintainable. This crop cutter might be the solution to the problems faced by a small-scale farmer regarding cost and worker implementation. Comparison of Harvesting Cost by Traditional Method and Our Harvester

1. Harvesting done by Manual process

Amount paid to the labour for one day = Rs. 300 per labour Total number of labours required in general to harvest the 1-acre farm in a day = 6
Total amount paid to the labour = $6 \times 300 = \text{Rs. } 1800$ per acre in one day. Therefore, total expenditure in one day is =Rs. 1800

2. Harvesting done by Crop Cutter Machine

Power required to charge the 2 batteries of 12V 7.5Amp
=180 watts Cost of 1 unit of electricity =5.90 rupees
For 180 watts of power, it costs = 1.62 rupees
Amount paid to the labour +Maintenance cost+ charging cost
 $300+60+1.62= 361.2$.

Result: From the above discussion the amount saved by using harvester is shown below $1800-361.2= 1438.8$ rupees.

Fig. 3: Machine cutting Plants

Fig. 4: Complete Cutter Machine

5. Design Model of the Cutter Machine

Fig.5: 3D Model of the Cutter Machine

The Fig 5 represents the cutter machine 3D model developed according to the required dimensions using the CATIA software tool this model helped in the Conceptual design of the

cutter machine model and Fig 6 represents the orthographic views of the machine.

Fig.6: Views of the Cutter Machine

6. Design Calculations

TORQUE CALCULATION REQUIRED TO ROTATE THE WHEEL:

Mass = 20 kg

Wheel radius=

0.0381 mMax

velocity= 0.31 m/s

Speed = 90 rpm

Assuming the force to push would be the weight of the machine.

Moment of Inertia.

$I = 1/2. m. r^2$

Given mass = 20kg, radius

0.0381m $I = 20kg (0.0381m)^2$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \cdot 20 \cdot 0.00145041 \text{ kg.m}^2$$

$$= 0.0145041 \text{ kg m}^2$$

Angular Acceleration (α)

$$\text{Given Acceleration} = 1.3 \text{ m/s}^2 \quad r$$

$$= 0.0381 \text{ m} \alpha = a/r = 1.3/0.0381 =$$

$$34.12 \text{ rad /s}^2$$

$$\text{Torque} = I * \alpha = 0.0145041 \text{ Kg. m}^2 * 34.12 \text{ rad/s}^2$$

$$\text{Torque} = \mathbf{0.494 \text{ Nm.}}$$

7. Literature Review

Dilip Radkar (2021) et al: In this machine farmer is walking with machine during seed sowing and ploughing, providing seating arrangement into the machine will be beneficial. In multipurpose machine in addition to ploughing and seed sowing, the arrangement for fertilizer and manure can be made [1].

Nair Ashwin.A (2020) et al: Practically this multipurpose agricultural equipment can be used for tilling, ploughing, seeding, weeding and for levelling purposes. All the parts are connected in such a way that in every stage of agriculture the equipment can be rearranged or easily assembled with fasteners to required specifications of field operation in a modular way [2].

Mahesh Kadam (2021) et al: This system reduces the cost of harvesting up to 60-70 % as that of case conventional method. In to use the machine in case of sugarcane application we can provide more power at prime mover one spring in parallel, let us say 4 parallel springs can be used to increase the capacity [3].

Dr.U.V. Kongrel (2016) et al: This work was carried out with objective to design, modification and evaluate the performance of Manual operated reaper [4].

Krunal Mudafale (2022) et al: The mechanism employed, the scotch yoke mechanism, does not perform as expected. Another mechanism can be used to improve this efficiency. and the motor's speed is reduced since use of heavy materials, which might be substituted with lighter materials [5].

Prajakt Paithankar (2017) et al: If we use crop cutting machine it consumes 3.7 units approximate to cultivate 1 Acer farm. By replacing the motor, we can use wheel operated cutter rotation by using the sprocket, chain. [6].

Vishal Ullegaddi (2019) et al: Suitable cutting mechanism and crop collection mechanism for crop harvester was designed, analyzed and fabricated. It was found that cutting mechanism was able to work under different farm conditions. [7]

Akshay Patil (2023) et al: The concept is defined in this initial phase followed by a very simple design that continues throughout the project The machine running time is about two hours continuous which can it work in one time charge of battery [8]

Muntasim Bhaijanl (2023) et al: The utilization of a crop cutter system can lead to a substantial reduction in harvesting costs, typically ranging from 60% to 70% compared to conventional methods. To enhance efficiency, curved collectors can be added to the sides of the crop cutter. These collectors would gather the cut crops and automate the process of tying them into bunches. The bundled crops can then be expelled at the rear of the cutter for easier collection and handling [10]

Vilas S. Gadhav (2017) et al: This study is to design and fabricate the machinery which can reduce dependency on workers which give much effect to our country in increasing the profits for the farmers. To design and fabricate this machine, there are many criteria are selected such as easy to manufacture, low cost in long term, and can harvest high and with much easy to use [11]

6. Conclusion

The design and development of the multipurpose crop cutting machine utilizing battery power, a microcontroller, camera, DC motor, and Android-based control system represents a significant advancement in agricultural automation. Through the integration of these technologies, the machine offers the capability to autonomously navigate fields, identify crops using its camera system, and execute precise cutting operations without human intervention. This innovative solution addresses the challenges faced by farmers in labor-intensive crop harvesting while improving efficiency and productivity. With its user-friendly Android control interface, the machine offers ease of operation and monitoring, further enhancing its practicality and accessibility. Overall, the successful implementation of this project demonstrates its potential to revolutionize agricultural practices, making crop harvesting more efficient, cost-effective, and sustainable.

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